

SYNERGETIC ENHANCEMENT OF THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY BY ALUMINA NANOWIRES IN EPOXY COMPOSITES CONTAINING MICRO FILLERS

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ABSTRACT

Thermally conductive polymer composites offer new possibilities for the thermal management in electronic devices. An approach of current interest to improve the thermal conductivity of polymer composites is the addition of hybrid nano and micro fillers with high thermal conductivity. The objective of this paper is to study the effective thermal conductivity of the epoxy composites with nano and micro fillers. The nano filler used was alumina nanowires, and the alumina and boron nitride particles with different shape and size were selected as the micro fillers. Representative volume element (RVE) models with the random close-packed structures of micro fillers were obtained using MacroPac software and Digmat-FE software, and finite element analysis of the thermal conductivity of the RVE models was conducted using Digmat-FE software. In addition, experimental measurements of the thermal conductivity of the manufactured polymer composites were carried out by using a steady-state method. The results showed that the addition of nano fillers to the matrix increased the thermal conductivity of the composites with close-packed structure of micro fillers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Most polymers have very low thermal conductivity. One approach to improving thermal conductivity of polymers is through the addition of thermally conductive fillers, such as ceramics, carbons and metals. The advantages of the polymer composite with thermally conductive fillers as compared to metals include improved corrosion resistance and lighter weight. For example, high thermally conductive composite is ideally suited for heat sink applications in electric systems [1].

An approach of current interest to improve the thermal conductivity of polymers is the selective addition of nano fillers with high aspect ratio and high thermal conductivity such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs). When nano fillers with high aspect ratio and high thermal conductivity are dispersed in polymer, an interconnecting network is formed which provides a pathway for heat conduction. However, due to their nanoscale dimension and high aspect ratio, thermally conductive composites with high volume fractions of well-dispersed nano fillers are not easily obtained.

Processing of polymer composites with high volume fractions of fillers is difficult due to the addition of fillers leading to high viscosity. To achieve the high thermal conductivity by the addition of low volume fractions of fillers, synergy effects of nano and micro fillers has been addressed by many authors [2-4]. Sanada et al. [5] fabricated the composites with CNTs and the random close-packed structure of alumina micro particles and investigated the potential of CNTs to enhance thermal conductivity of the composites. When the composites have a random close-packed structure of micro fillers, CNTs and micro fillers show a good interconnectivity causing a large increase in thermal conductivity of the composites. The objective of this paper is to develop high thermally conductive composites with hybrid fillers containing alumina nanowires (ANWs) and micro fillers. ANWs have high aspect ratio, high thermal conductivity and high electrical resistivity. One promising application of ANWs is as interconnecting fillers in the composites to provide enhanced thermal conductivity and retained electrical insulation.

2 EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION

Composite resins were prepared by mixing Epikote 828 epoxy resin from Japan Epoxy Resins Co., Ltd. with NH-2200 curing agent from Hitachi Chemical Co., Ltd., Epikure BMI12 accelerator from Japan Epoxy Resins Co., Ltd. and hybrid fillers using an AR-250 planetary centrifugal mixer (THINKY Co.). The mix ratio of Epikote 828, NH-2200 and Epikure BMI12 was 100:80:2 by weight.

The hybrid fillers consisted of nano and micro fillers. Nano fillers used were ANWs (average diameter of 2-4nm, average length of 200-400 μ m) and multi-walled CNTs (average diameter of 6-9nm, average length of 5 μ m) from Sigma-Aldrich. Micro fillers used were alumina and boron nitride (BN) particles from Denki Kagaku Kogyo Co., Ltd. Two grades of alumina particle, i.e. DAW05 (average diameter of 3.7-7.5 μ m) and DAW10 (average diameter of 7.5-11.5 μ m), were used. The alumina particle had a perfect spherical shape. Two grades of BN particle, i.e. GP (average particle size of 8 μ m) and SGP (average particle size of 18 μ m), were selected. The BN particle had a flake-like shape. All the above fillers were used as received. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of nano and micro fillers are shown in Figure 1. The densities of the ANW, CNT, alumina, BN and epoxy resin were 4g/cm³, 1.75g/cm³, 3.98g/cm³, 2.26g/cm³ and 1.2g/cm³, respectively.

Figure 1: SEM images of nano and micro fillers: (a) ANW; (b) CNT; (c) alumina (DAW05); (d) BN (GP)

In the case of the composites containing nano and micro fillers, the matrix is a two-phase composite composed of nano fillers and epoxy resin. Thus, the micro filler volume fraction V_f^M in the composites containing nano and micro fillers is given by

$$V_f^M = \frac{V_M}{V_M + V_m^*} \quad (1)$$

where V_M and V_m^* are the volume of the micro fillers and the matrix containing nano fillers, respectively. The nano filler volume fraction V_f^N is defined as

$$V_f^N = \frac{V_N}{V_m^*} = \frac{V_N}{V_N + V_m} \quad (2)$$

where V_N and V_m are the volume of the nano fillers and the epoxy resin, respectively.

The composite resins were then molded at 100°C for 2h, followed by post-curing at 150°C for 4h. The samples were composite disks of 50mm in diameter and 10-15mm in thickness. Thermal conductivities of the composites were measured by using the steady-state technique with a HC-110 thermal conductivity tester (Eiko Instruments Co., Ltd.).

3 NUMERICAL APPROACH

A Monte-Carlo algorithm implemented in the MacroPac software from Intelligensys Ltd. and the Digimat-FE software from MSC Software Corp. was used to generate representative volume element (RVE) with two-filler system with the random close-packed structure of micro fillers. Micro fillers are randomly placed into a matrix, with the restriction that they cannot overlap each other. Once the required volume fraction is achieved, the generation process of the RVE is terminated. For the RVE with close-packed structure, the generation process is repeated until insufficient free volume is available for creating a new filler. Figure 2 shows RVE models of random close-packed structures of DAW10/DAW05 and SGP/GP system. For two-filler system, the micro filler volume fraction V_f^M is given by

$$V_f^M = \frac{V_1 N_1 + V_2 N_2}{L^3} \quad (3)$$

where V_1 is the volume of a large micro filler, V_2 is the volume of a small micro filler, N_1 is the number of large micro fillers, N_2 is the number of small micro fillers and L is the unit cell dimension. The filler size ratio is defined as $\alpha = \sqrt[3]{V_1 / V_2}$.

Figure 2: RVE models of random close-packed structures of micro fillers (hard boundary condition) : (a) DAW10/DAW05; (b) SGP/GP

Using the Digimat-FE software, the steady-state thermal problem for RVE models was solved and the thermal conductivity was evaluated. The volumes comprising the fillers and the matrix are meshed using tetrahedral elements. Computations of the thermal conductivity were done for the RVE models in three axis directions. Hence, the average effective thermal conductivity is given by

$$\lambda_c^{\text{FEM}} = \frac{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3}{3} \quad (4)$$

The individual phase materials are modeled as homogeneous solids and perfect bonding between the phases is assumed. The thermal conductivities of the ANW, CNT and alumina are 36W/mK, 3000W/mK and 36W/mK, respectively. The BN particles are transverse isotropic materials having the thermal conductivities of 250W/mK (in-plane direction) and 1W/mK (thickness direction). For the epoxy resin, the specimens were prepared and its thermal conductivity was measured using the steady-state method. The measured thermal conductivity of the epoxy resin is 0.163W/mK.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the theoretical maximum packing conditions for DAW10/DAW05 and SGP/GP systems obtained using MacroPac software. Using these results for hard boundary condition, the samples of DAW10/DAW05 and SGP/GP composites were prepared, and thermal conductivity measurements were conducted.

Table 1: Theoretical maximum packing conditions

System	Boundary condition	Composition of fillers		Maximum volume fraction (%)
		Large filler	Small filler	
DAW10/DAW05	Hard	0.700	0.300	47.5
	Periodic	0.729	0.271	50.8
SGP/GP	Hard	0.645	0.355	33.8
	Periodic	0.668	0.332	34.9

The effect of addition of ANWs ($V_f^N = 3\text{vol}\%$) to the matrix on the measured thermal conductivity of DAW10/DAW05 composites at $V_f^M = 30$ and $50\text{vol}\%$ is shown in Figure 3. The results indicate that the improvement in the thermal conductivity of the composite is attained through the addition of ANWs. The effectiveness of ANWs is increased at the higher V_f^M .

Figure 3: Effect of addition of ANWs to the matrix on the measured thermal conductivity of DAW10/DAW05 composites

Figure 4 presents the effect of nano filler type on the measured thermal conductivity of DAW10/DAW05 composites containing nano fillers ($V_f^M = 50\text{vol}\%$ and $V_f^N = 3\text{vol}\%$). Though the

ANWs (36W/mK) have a lower thermal conductivity as compared to the CNTs (3000W/mK), two composites have almost the same thermal conductivity. Better thermal conductivity of the composites containing ANWs could be achieved due to improved dispersion of the ANWs and interfacial properties between the ANW and the epoxy resin.

Figure 4: Effect of nano filler type on the measured thermal conductivity of DAW10/DAW05 composites containing nano fillers

The thermal conductivities of SGP/GP/ANW composites and DAW10/DAW05/ANW composites ($V_f^M = 30\text{vol}\%$ and $V_f^N = 3\text{vol}\%$) are shown in Figure 5. The thermal conductivity of SGP/GP/ANW composites is higher than that of DAW10/DAW05/ANW composites.

Figure 5: Thermal conductivities of SGP/GP/ANW and DAW10/DAW05/ANW composites

Figure 6 presents the experimental data for the thermal conductivities of SGP/GP and DAW10/DAW05 composites, together with the predictions for RVE model with two-filler system with the random close-packed structure of micro fillers. The predictions were slightly lower than the experimental data.

Figure 6: Experimental data and predictions for thermal conductivities of SGP/GP and DAW10/DAW05 composites

5 CONCLUSIONS

The composites with random close-packed structure of ANW and micro fillers were fabricated and the potential of ANWs to enhance thermal conductivity of the composites was investigated. The addition of ANWs to the epoxy matrix between the micro fillers increased the thermal conductivity of the composites and the effectiveness of ANWs was increased at the higher micro filler volume fraction. Though the thermal conductivities of ANW and CNT were significantly different, the thermal conductivities of DAW10/DAW05/ANW and DAW10/DAW05/CNT composites were identical. The close-packed structure of nano and micro fillers can form thermally conducting pathways more easily than that of only micro fillers.

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